

ESM2025 outputs : High level summary

November 2025

INTRODUCTION

Human civilisation depends on interconnected Earth Systems – such as the atmosphere, oceans, land and biosphere – for essentials like clean air, water, food and a stable climate. Earth System Models (ESMs) provide an important scientific basis for understanding how human activity affects and is affected by these systems and are important for informing policy action, both for mitigation and adaptation to global climate change. However, certain questions around the design of strategies to pursue the goals of the Paris Agreement could still benefit from further development and improvement of ESMs.

ESM2025 – Earth system models for the future is a European research project on Earth System modelling that has built the next generation of European ESMs focussed on informing how efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (referred to as climate change mitigation) interact with our planetary Earth System. These models will help to provide valuable scientific insights to support successful implementation of the Paris Agreement.

The new models provide more complete and realistic representations of key Earth Systems and

their responses to human-caused emissions of greenhouse gases and land-use change. They will be able to provide essential scientific evidence for developing climate mitigation strategies as well as robust guidance on future global environmental risks, supporting policies targeting adaptation to global change.

The project ran from June 2021 – November 2025. This briefing provides a summary of the key improvements that have been made to Earth System models, the ways in which this will help to support policymaking and key findings from model outputs.

ABOUT THE TEAM

Led by Météo France-CNRM, the project consisted of an interdisciplinary team of 21 partners from 7 countries across Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK) and Australia.

The project' team was composed of Earth-System scientists and model developers, experts in machine learning and data-driven hybrid modelling, model evaluation and feedback analysis, as well as specialists in integrated assessment models, climate education and science-policy communication.

How have Earth System Models been improved?

The ESM2025 project has delivered multiple improvements to Earth System models, making them more realistic and robust.

The project's Earth System models can now make simulations that respond to emissions (not just prescribed concentrations), not only for carbon dioxide, but also for methane.

Improved simulation of nitrogen flows (including from agriculture), how they affect plant growth, carbon uptake, and the release of nitrous oxide (a potent greenhouse gas).

More complete picture of how land, soil and plants contribute to both climate warming and cooling, including nutrient limits, non-CO₂ land emissions, and the varying side-effects of land management.

Improved representation of how rivers link the land and ocean, with a more detailed description of carbon and nitrogen transport, refining how much carbon dioxide the ocean can actually absorb and how coastal biogeochemistry changes.

Enhanced simulation of how ice sheets interact with the climate system, including feedbacks and response to warming, and how that may impact long-term sea level rise.

Greater consistency between Earth System and Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs)—which include representations of the economy and society—with improved traceability of uncertainties across the modelling chain (for example for land-based mitigation options).

More realistic representation of methane, including emissions from wetlands, lakes, wildfires and thawing permafrost, and the atmospheric chemistry that controls methane's lifetime.

More realistic representation of ocean dynamics and biogeochemistry, improving mixing processes, large-scale circulation and marine nutrient cycling, which is relevant for heat and carbon uptake.

Improved representation of wildfires, which now includes human factors (ignitions, suppression, land management) and their impact on carbon emissions, vegetation growth and air quality, under a changing climate.

What policy questions can these improved models help to address?

Projecting impacts, understanding risks and anticipating tipping points

- ▶ How are temperatures projected to increase under different scenarios?
 - ▶ How will ecosystems change as a result?
- ▶ What are the future risks linked to polar ice loss?
 - ▶ How much will sea levels rise?
 - ▶ What adaptation will be needed in coastal areas?
 - ▶ What is the risk of triggering irreversible tipping points?
- ▶ What are the future risks to food security?
- ▶ How might wildfires affect land management and environmental health? And what are the risks of negative feedbacks?
- ▶ Will warming stop when we stop global carbon dioxide emissions?

Evaluating and informing climate strategies

- ▶ How much carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases can we still emit while staying below 1.5°C or 2°C?
 - ▶ How much carbon can we expect the ocean to absorb and what does this mean for global carbon budgets?
 - ▶ How does land use and land management affect temperature and carbon dioxide storage?
- ▶ What impact will methane pledges have on avoiding warming?

Assessing the effectiveness of different carbon reduction and removal options

- ▶ Which mitigation strategies are most robust (performing well across uncertainties, avoiding reliance on risky assumptions and aligning with multiple sustainability goals)?
- ▶ Which types of emissions cuts and carbon removal pathways are more likely to limit warming?
- ▶ Which types of mitigation carry risks or potential unintended consequences?
- ▶ How might land-based mitigation strategies like afforestation or bioenergy crops behave under future climate conditions?

Key findings

- 1. Achieving net zero carbon dioxide is essential to halt global warming.**
Emissions reductions alone are not enough.

- 2. Substantial reductions in non-carbon dioxide emissions are needed urgently.**
Without them, remaining carbon budgets compatible with the Paris Agreement may already be exhausted. In particular, strong methane reductions are essential as methane is responsible for nearly half of today's warming.

- 3. Over-relying on land-based removals (such as afforestation and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage – BECCS) could make it harder to meet climate goals:**
 - Models show that the ability to store carbon in trees, plants and soil may weaken over time, especially in warmer and drier conditions.
 - Large-scale bioenergy crops can compete with food production and strain water resources.
 - Coordinated ESM-IAM analyses show large uncertainties in the effectiveness of land-based mitigation and results are sensitive to both Earth-system feedbacks and socio-economic assumptions.

- 4. Exceeding 1.5°C will increase the risks that we face, including increasing the likelihood of crossing tipping points.** So-called “overshoot” pathways (that is, pathways where global warming temporarily exceeds 1.5°C before being brought back down again by removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere) carry additional climate and Earth system risks, including increased likelihood of crossing tipping points.

- 5. Linking Earth system and socio-economic modelling improves the credibility of scenarios.**
ESM-IAM integration makes pathways physically consistent, clarifies where results hinge on Earth-system feedbacks as opposed to socio-economic assumptions, and helps test the robustness of land-based options under uncertainty.

FURTHER INFORMATION

ESM2025 website: www.esm2025.eu

ESM2025 research (data, tools and publications): www.esm2025.eu/research/

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